

IPerGlio
#ERA PerMed

Stakeholder Guidelines for Publishing Patient Data on
Publicly Available Dashboards

IPerGlio

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Publicly Available Dashboards

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Organization & Facilitation

Simone Krieger

Ruben Andreas Sakowsky

Amirali Jahani Yazdi

Layout: Amirali Jahani Yazdi

Stakeholders

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Elena Anghileri

Fondazione IRCCS Istituto Neurologico Carlo Besta via Celoria, Italy

Marina Cuadrado Ruiz

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John de Bruin

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University Medical Centre of Göttingen, Germany

Milena Ivanova

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Rolf J. Ledal

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Preface

Dear readers,

Thank you for your interest in this document, *Stakeholder Guidelines for Publishing Patient Data on Publicly Available Dashboards*. The ethical management of patient data on public dashboards is a matter of growing importance in biomedical research. While the need for open and accessible access to scientific findings is undeniable, it must always be pursued with a strong commitment to safeguarding patient rights and privacy.

As part of the *IPerGlio* project, a pan-European research endeavour spanning Norway, Italy, Luxembourg, Spain, and Germany, we are striving to identify prognostic markers that will enhance the quality of care for glioblastoma (GBM) patients. However, our commitment goes beyond scientific discovery: we aim to make our findings available to the public in the most accessible manner possible and we seek to do so in an ethically responsible manner, incorporating the perspectives and needs of all relevant stakeholders.

To this end, we conducted an online Stakeholder Consensus Conference (SCC) in September/October 2024 with participants hailing from Norway, Italy, Spain, Romania, Netherlands, Belgium, UK, and Germany. The participants took on the important task of addressing how research data can be shared on a public dashboard while respecting ethical considerations. By bringing together a diverse group of stakeholders, including patient representatives, healthcare professionals, bioethicists, and researchers, we engaged in an open

dialogue about privacy, consent, data security, and the appropriate use of medical data.

This document presents the insights and recommendations that emerged from this process. It is authored by our stakeholders and the result of a collective and collaborative effort to ensure that scientific progress does not come at the cost of ethical compromise. While our stakeholders focused on the context of glioblastoma research, we hope that these guidelines will serve as a valuable resource for researchers and policymakers navigating the challenges of public data sharing in medical research in general.

On behalf of the ethics team and the *IPerGlio* consortium, we would like to express our deepest gratitude to all stakeholders who participated in this conference. Your engagement, expertise, and dedication have been instrumental in shaping a framework that prioritizes transparency, responsibility, and patient-centred values.

We look forward to continuing this important conversation and working together towards ethically responsible biomedical research.

Sincerely,

The IPerGlio Germany team

Ruben A. Sakowsky, Simone Krieger,

Amirali Jahani Yazdi

The IPerGlio Team

Introduction

Introduction

Glioblastoma (GBM) is an aggressive and deadly form of brain cancer with a median survival rate of less than 15 months. While brain cancers are relatively rare compared to other types of cancer, GBM is the most common. The standard treatment for GBM has remained largely unchanged for almost 20 years, highlighting the urgent need for new therapeutic strategies. Immunotherapies, which leverage the body's immune system to combat cancer, have shown promise in the very small subgroup of patients that experienced it, with 10-20% of patients experiencing long-term survival benefits. However, due to the variability in disease presentation and progression, there is a critical lack of reliable biomarkers that can guide personalized treatment decisions.

To address this challenge, the international research project “Improving personalized GBM care by intertwined immunomics and artificial intelligence approaches” (IPerGlio) brings together researchers from Norway, Italy, Luxembourg, Spain, and Germany. The clinical centres in Norway and Italy collect comprehensive patient data, including demographic and clinical information, lifestyle factors, and biological samples. These data, combined with publicly available datasets, are analysed using artificial intelligence (AI) in Luxembourg and Spain to identify patterns that could enhance GBM treatment strategies.

IPerGlio is funded by the European Research Area Network for Personalized Medicine (ERA PerMed), a European research consortium cofounded by the European Commission.

A key goal of the project is to contribute to the dissemination of knowledge about GBM by making research results publicly available on a dashboard designed to be as accessible as possible for lay users. However, this raises significant ethical concerns regarding data security, privacy, and the appropriate use of patient information. To navigate these complex issues, the German project partner at the University of Potsdam has organized a Stakeholder Consensus Conference (SCC) to explore how a publicly accessible dashboard can be established in an ethically responsible manner. While the focus of the SCC was on the context of the IPerGlio dashboard, stakeholders were asked to produce general guidelines that may provide guidance for researchers seeking to utilize patient data to create public dashboards in other settings.

Stakeholder Consensus Conferences (SCCs)

SCCs are structured deliberative meetings that bring together diverse stakeholders, such as patient organization representatives, health professionals, and domain experts, to discuss, deliberate, and, ideally, reach a consensus on, critical topics.

SCCs aim at ensuring that all perspectives are considered, fostering mutual understanding and collaboration.

In the context of IPerGlio, the SCC aimed at developing ethical guidelines for research data publication (including pseudonymized patient data) while addressing potential risks and benefits.

While IPerGlio patients have consented to the pseudonymised release of their data, and ethics approval for the launch of the dashboard has been obtained, ethical concerns extend beyond individual consent and necessitate further discussion. Important questions include:

- What are the normative principles stakeholders think should guide publication decisions?
- How should risks for patients, such as misuse of the data by third parties, be weighed against the educational benefits of the dashboard?
- How can we maximize the benefit users derive from the dashboard?
- How can we make sure patients understand what happens with their data?
- How can the dashboard be made as accessible as possible?

These questions underscore the complexity of ethical decision-making in medical research. Our SCC explored these concerns in depth and provides recommendations for ethical data management.

Conference Structure and Methodology

To ensure a well-organized and productive conference, a structured agenda was developed, including:

- Preparatory meetings with participants and domain experts in GBM research, data publishing, data ethics, and data privacy law
- Expert presentations on the IPerGlio project, data sharing, and the ethical and legal implications of patient data publication
- Discussion rounds and small group work sessions to develop recommendations
- Plenary discussions of developed results
- Use of online whiteboards for structured collaboration
- Networking sessions to foster deeper connections among participants
- Voting rounds to refine and finalise consensus recommendations

Given the online format of the SCC, we leveraged the online whiteboard function of the telecommunication software Zoom to facilitate structured discussions. This tool enabled collaborative idea development and ensured that absent participants could quickly catch up. Whiteboard content and written notes were used for documentation.

We asked our stakeholders to produce two outcome documents: (1) an information brochure for patients donating their data to the IPerGlio project that explains the data journey in a lay-accessible manner, and (2) a guideline for researchers engaged in creating data

dashboards that tackles the previously mentioned ethical questions. The latter task resulted in this document which contains valuable information about what our stakeholders value.

Opportunities and Challenges of Online Deliberation

Conducting an SCC online present both opportunities and challenges. Online formats enhance accessibility, allowing stakeholders to participate regardless of location. Additionally, digital collaboration tools provide structured, real-time and asynchronous engagement and documentation. However, challenges include managing technical difficulties and maintaining participant engagement over extended and often mentally taxing virtual discussions. Despite these challenges, the SCC represented a successful effort in leveraging online deliberation for patient-centred research ethics. Through mutual learning and open discussion, we aimed at producing clear ethical guidelines for the IPerGlio dashboard and patient information efforts, as well as broader recommendations for the publication of patient data in research dissemination efforts.

The following text is the result of the collaborative efforts of our stakeholders to produce a comprehensive guideline for the ethical publication of patient data on a public dashboard. It has been edited for clarity by the IPerGlio Team.

Stakeholder Recommendations

Stakeholder Recommendations

Background

We are a group of 11 stakeholders from 8 European countries who came together in September and October 2024 at the invitation of the EraPerMed project IPerGlio to discuss the public disclosure of pseudonymised patient data through a publicly accessible data dashboard. Our group includes current and former caregivers, professional nurses, and representatives of patient organizations. Many of us have personal experiences with cancer, either through our own experiences or those of our loved ones.

GBM is an exceptionally aggressive form of primary brain cancer, and there is an urgent need for innovative treatment strategies to improve patient care. Among other experimental clinical trials, some have evaluated immunotherapies that harness the body's immune system to fight the cancer, reporting long-term survival benefits in some patients. However, because the disease presents and progresses differently among individuals, and because of the very heterogeneous nature of how immune systems present in different patients, there is currently a lack of clear indicators to guide researchers and physicians in selecting the best course of action for each patient. The IPerGlio project seeks to address this critical issue.

IPerGlio is an international research initiative that unites experts from Norway, Italy, Luxembourg, Spain, and Germany. Clinical centres in Norway and Italy collect patient data, including

demographic and clinical information, lifestyle details, blood samples, and tumour samples, which is then combined with data from public databases and analysed by partners in Luxembourg and Spain, with the assistance of artificial intelligence (AI). IPerGlio aims to identify patterns in patient data that will inform decision-making in GBM care. The results of this research are intended to be made publicly available through a data dashboard. The IPerGlio team has sought our guidance on determining what information the dashboard should include and how it should engage its users.

With these guidelines, we express our values, concerns, and preferences regarding the design and implementation of a public dashboard. While our primary audience is the IPerGlio team responsible for producing the dashboard, we also hope that this text will offer useful guidance to other researchers aiming to make research data available to the public.

Our Values

The well-being of patients, along with that of their families and loved ones, is our primary concern. This encompasses both physical and mental health, as we recognize that the well-being of patients is inextricably linked to that of their support networks. We believe that emphasizing quality of life—rather than focusing solely on patient survival—is essential. Enhancing health literacy by

ensuring that patients and caregivers understand their situation can significantly contribute to their overall well-being.

Health data offers substantial benefits to both patient communities and society at large. It can facilitate clinical decision-making and drive further research. However, these benefits must be carefully balanced against the rights of individual patients to control their own data.

We believe that deepening our understanding of GBM is a crucial goal. We also believe that patients and their caregivers should be well-informed, with information presented in an accessible and easily understandable manner. Moreover, we advocate for a close, collaborative relationship between patients, their loved ones, and healthcare professionals to facilitate shared decision-making. We support robust communication and information exchange between researchers and patients, and we believe that these relationships should be actively fostered. In addition, loved ones can often provide vital insights into the patient's condition and needs that the patient might overlook or be hesitant to share; at the same time, they may need support to better cope with the situation.

Maintaining hope is another core value. It is vital for patients and caregivers to remain hopeful that better treatments for GBM will become available, not only for themselves but for others as well. Empowering patients and caregivers to contribute to this goal is essential.

Finally, we believe that trust in the integrity of research is paramount. This trust should be nurtured through maximum transparency and by adopting best practices in the publication of patient data. It is also important to recognize the neurological changes patients may experience as the disease progresses, particularly those associated with cognitive, behavioural and potentially psychiatric deficits. Adequate support should be provided not only for patients but also for their families, helping them understand and cope with these challenges.

Our Concerns

GBM patients and their caregivers often face significant uncertainty about the disease and the future. They may not know what to expect, or how to prepare for what lies ahead. This uncertainty is particularly challenging when patients must make decisions about treatment options. Clear and accessible guidance is crucial during this time.

Unfortunately, much of the information currently available is difficult for a non-professional to understand. It often includes complex medical and legal terms that many patients and caregivers are not equipped to interpret. Even when information is presented, its volume and complexity, combined with the emotional burden caused by the diagnosis, can make it overwhelming, leaving patients and families unsure about how to use it to make informed decisions.

It is also important to ensure that patients are not burdened with information that is irrelevant to their specific situation.

Overloading them with unnecessary, confusing, or needlessly frightening details can lead to additional stress, which should be avoided whenever possible.

Caregivers and loved ones play a vital role in the care of GBM patients. In many cases, patients may not be able to assess their own condition accurately due to the neurological impacts of the disease. Caregivers often step in to provide essential observations and support, making their inclusion in the care process indispensable.

In light of these challenges, we believe the following actions should be prioritized in the development of a public dashboard:

More Widely Available Information: Accessible information should be made more widely available to patients, families, and caregivers.

Accessible and Clear Communication: All information should be presented in simple, easy-to-understand language, avoiding unnecessary or technical terms. Materials should also be translated into the patient's native language whenever possible, particularly for medical terminology.

Relevance of Information: The dashboard should prioritize presenting information that is directly relevant to the patient's condition and treatment journey. This minimizes unnecessary worry and helps focus on actionable insights.

Caregiver Involvement: The role of caregivers and loved ones as active participants in the patient's care should be recognized and supported. The

database should include resources specifically tailored to their needs.

Safeguards Against Misuse: While public dashboards are a valuable resource, they can also be vulnerable to misuse, such as by commercial entities. Although this issue may not be fully solvable, efforts should be made to implement safeguards that protect patient data and ensure its ethical use.

By addressing these concerns, the resulting dashboard should aim to be informative, supportive, and respectful of the needs of glioblastoma patients and their caregivers.

Practical Recommendations

Based on the values and concerns we present practical recommendations in the following chapters for four areas we have identified as especially important for a public dashboard that is as helpful for patients and their caregivers as possible.

Provide information about the goals of the dashboard: To be as transparent as possible and to build trust in the research team, users of the dashboard should be provided with clear information about the goals and functions of the dashboard, its capabilities and limitations, as well as information about its operators and liability.

Privacy and consent: Patients who contribute data to the dashboard must be fully informed about how their data will be handled. Information should be presented in a clear and engaging manner.

Define user groups: The dashboard should serve multiple user groups, such as patients, caregivers, healthcare professionals, and researchers. These groups all have different needs that should be met by the dashboard. Importantly, the dashboard should also serve collaboration and communication between these groups.

Accessibility and Usability: The dashboard should be usable by all. Information must be presented in plain language, available in multiple languages, and supported by visual aids and glossaries to explain complex terms and data. The design should be mobile-friendly, visually accessible for those with impairments, and compatible with assistive technologies. A clean, organized interface will help users navigate easily and access relevant information without being overwhelmed.

Providing Information Beyond Research Data: The dashboard should provide more than scientific findings and offer practical guidance for patients and caregivers. It should link to clear resources on, among others, disease progression, and treatment side effects. The dashboard should include a directory of useful resources as well as an accessible Q&A section. Patient organizations can help ensure that the information provided is accurate and useful.

Provide information about the goals of the dashboard

Provide information about the goals of the dashboard

In the interest of transparency and to ensure trust in the research team, it is important to clearly communicate the goals and intended functions of the dashboard and prevent misunderstandings.

Goals and Functions of the IPerGlio Dashboard

The primary purpose of the IPerGlio public dashboard is to educate and inform users about GBM, its treatments, and related research. It aims to provide accessible, reliable, and clear information to patients, caregivers, healthcare professionals, and the public, fostering greater understanding of this aggressive disease and the potential advancements in care.

Transparency and Operator Information

To build trust and confidence, it is essential that users understand who is behind the dashboard and what its purpose is. The dashboard is operated by the IPerGlio research team, which is a non-commercial entity dedicated to improving GBM care through interdisciplinary research. A clear disclaimer will state that the dashboard is operated solely for research and educational purposes, not for profit or commercial gain.

Educational Functionality

The dashboard is intended as an educational tool and not a substitute for

medical advice. Users should be aware that: (1) The information provided in the dashboard is based on research and data analysis. (2) While the dashboard offers valuable insights, it is not equipped to give personalized medical advice or guidance. (3) Patients should consult their healthcare providers for any decisions regarding their care or treatment.

Capabilities and Limitations

To set realistic expectations, the dashboard should explicitly outline what it can and cannot do. The dashboard **can** provide: (1) General information about glioblastoma and its progression. (2) Research findings, including insights from data patterns that might guide future care. (3) Resources to improve health literacy for patients and caregivers. The dashboard **cannot** provide: (1) Medical diagnoses or treatment recommendations. (2) Individualized patient care guidance.

Liability Information

It is important to clearly communicate to users via liability disclaimers that: (1) The dashboard does not assume responsibility for medical decisions made based on the information it provides. (2) Users are strongly encouraged to consult qualified medical professionals before acting on any information from the dashboard. (3) The IPerGlio team will take reasonable measures to ensure the accuracy of the information presented but cannot

guarantee its applicability to every user's unique situation.

By maintaining transparency, outlining its educational purpose, and providing clear disclaimers, the dashboard should seek to support users with knowledge resources while managing expectations responsibly.

Define user groups

Define User Groups

The dashboard should serve the needs of different audiences. Defining and understanding key user groups as well as how they interact is key to ensuring the dashboard's utility for all.

Key User Groups

Patients: The dashboard is a resource for patients to understand their condition and potential treatment options. It provides simplified, accessible information to help patients make informed decisions about their care. The information should be easy to navigate, free of complex medical terms, and visually clear to help patients understand their disease and treatment possibilities.

Caregivers: Caregivers play a crucial role in a patient's well-being, and their understanding of the disease and its progression is essential for providing effective support. The dashboard must be designed with caregivers in mind, offering them the resources they need to support patients emotionally and practically. Caregivers should have access to information on how to help the patient navigate their condition, understand medical advice, and manage daily care responsibilities.

Healthcare Professionals: Healthcare providers use the dashboard to access updated research and insights into the disease, which can inform their treatment plans. The dashboard should support healthcare professionals by offering in-depth clinical data, research findings, and tools for collaboration with patients and other health professionals. It should help them engage in shared decision-making

with patients and provide them with relevant, evidence-based information for care management.

Researchers: The dashboard serves as a valuable resource for researchers working to advance GBM treatment and care. It provides an intuitive way of understanding patterns in GBM data. This can drive further studies and hence improvements in treatment approaches.

Understanding Relationships Between Actors

It is essential to recognize the interconnections between different user groups, especially between caregivers and patients and healthcare professionals and patients.

Caregivers and Patients: Caregivers often have a deep understanding of a patient's state and can offer valuable insights into their well-being. They also play a crucial role in helping patients understand the information in the dashboard, making it essential for caregivers to have access to tailored content that empowers them to assist effectively.

Healthcare Professionals and Patients: The dashboard offers healthcare professionals an opportunity to engage with patients in a meaningful way. A well-designed dashboard allows both parties to explore the data together, facilitating shared decision-making and improving communication. It should allow healthcare providers to discuss information with patients in real-time, making it easier for both to explore

treatment options and navigate complex decisions.

Supporting Collaboration

The dashboard is not just a resource for individuals. It should foster collaboration between patients, caregivers, healthcare professionals, and researchers. By providing the right information for each group while considering their interdependence, the dashboard can play a key role in improving the quality of care, enhancing communication, advancing research and support networks. The ultimate aim is to raise awareness and enhance knowledge and care.

Privacy and Consent

Privacy and Consent

Patients who contribute data to the dashboard must be fully informed about their rights, including the ability to withdraw their consent within a specified timeframe. Clear, accessible information should explain what withdrawing consent entails, including details on when data withdrawal is no longer possible because the data has already been aggregated for research purposes. In addition, the process should provide patients with information about how their data will be handled after their death. This aspect should be communicated transparently and visualized using easy-to-understand approach to ensure clarity and accessibility.

Clear Expectations About Data Sharing

It is essential that patients have realistic expectations about the impact of sharing their data. The dashboard should communicate exactly how their data will be used, including its purpose in advancing research, supporting educational goals, and contributing to the development of new treatment options. At the time of, or prior to, obtaining consent, patients should receive detailed information about the specific uses of their data and the dashboard. This includes an explanation of how they can access the dashboard themselves and benefit from the educational content, helping them understand their condition better. Sharing their data should provide patients with a direct benefit, such as the opportunity to become better informed about their disease and available treatment options.

The Consent Process

The consent form for data donation should be simple, clear, and engaging. It must be written in plain language, avoiding any complex legal or medical terms. The goal is to ensure the form is easy to read and comprehend, leaving no room for misunderstandings or surprises for the patients.

Handling Incidental Findings

Patients should also be informed about how incidental findings (unexpected discoveries that may arise from their data) will be handled. Clear procedures should be outlined for how such findings are communicated and whether any follow-up actions are necessary. This includes whether and how incidental findings should be communicated to relatives in the case of the patient's death. This should be part of the consent process, ensuring patients are aware of these possibilities.

By ensuring clear, transparent communication about privacy and consent, patients can make informed decisions about sharing their data, contributing to the dashboard in a way that respects their rights and provides tangible benefits for themselves and the broader community.

Accessibility and Usability

Accessibility and Usability

It is crucial that all users of the IPerGlio dashboard, including patients, caregivers, and healthcare professionals, can easily access and understand the information provided. To achieve this, the design of the dashboard must prioritize accessibility and usability, ensuring that it is clear, easy to navigate, and tailored to the needs of each user group.

Clear and Simple Language

Many patients and caregivers may not understand complex medical or legal language. Therefore, information on the dashboard should be presented in simple, easy-to-understand language. This ensures that everyone, regardless of their medical background, can fully grasp important details about GBM, available and possible treatments, and factors influencing patient outcomes. By making information accessible, patients and caregivers can make more informed decisions regarding their care.

Mobile Accessibility

Recognizing that many patients and caregivers access the web primarily through smartphones, the design of the dashboard must be mobile-friendly. The dashboard should be fully responsive, meaning it adapts seamlessly to smaller screens, ensuring that users can easily access and navigate the content on their mobile devices.

Language Accessibility

Since many patients/caregivers may not speak English as their first language, the information in the dashboard should be available in the mother tongue of patients whenever possible. This helps ensure that language barriers do not prevent users from understanding important information related to GBM, treatment options, and research findings.

Simplifying Complex Information

Probabilities and statistical data, such as survival rates or treatment success rates, can be difficult for patients to interpret correctly. The dashboard should provide clear explanations and visual aids to help users understand these complex figures. For example, simple charts, visual representations, or step-by-step guides can help contextualize probabilities in a way that is easier to understand.

Glossary and Definitions

A glossary should be included in the dashboard to explain medical, legal and technical terms. This resource will provide definitions for specialized terms that might be unfamiliar to patients and caregivers, helping them better navigate the information. One useful resource to consider is the European Patients Academy for Therapeutic Innovation glossary,¹ which can provide standardized explanations of key medical terms.

¹ <https://toolbox.eupati.eu/glossary/>

Attractive, Simple Design

The design of the dashboard should be attractive yet simple to use, with a clean and organized layout. The interface should not overwhelm users with too many choices or complex options. Instead, it should focus on delivering the most important information in an intuitive and easy-to-navigate manner.

Consideration of Visual Impairments

To ensure that the dashboard is accessible to users with vision impairments, the design should be mindful of readability. This includes choosing high-contrast text, ensuring that fonts are legible, and providing the option to adjust font sizes.

Machine Accessibility

It is also important to make the dashboard machine-accessible. This ensures that users who rely on assistive technologies, such as screen readers, can navigate the dashboard effectively. The website should be compatible with these technologies and follow accessibility guidelines to ensure inclusivity for all users.

By focusing on these aspects of accessibility and usability, the dashboard can ensure that all patients, caregivers, and healthcare professionals can access the information they need, regardless of their technological proficiency or individual circumstances.

Providing Information Beyond Research Data

Providing Information Beyond Research Data

To ensure its educational function, the dashboard should go beyond presenting research findings and guide users to relevant resources for patients, caregivers, and their families. This ensures that users are provided with knowledge not only about the specific disease the dashboard is covering, but also about managing the illness and supporting the patient through each stage of the disease.

Practical Information for Patients and Caregivers

The dashboard should guide users to clear, practical information to help caregivers and patients understand the changes the patient is experiencing due to GBM. This should include insights into the disease, its progression, the neurological and cognitive changes associated with it, the emotional and psychological challenges associated with it, and possible treatment side-effects. Information on treatment options and their potential side effects should also be provided, so patients can better understand the benefits and risks of each option.

For the caregiver user group, the goal should be to help them better understand the patient's condition, communicate effectively with them, and provide appropriate care. Additionally, the dashboard should guide users to information on how caregivers can support patients with day-to-day

activities, help them navigate medical treatments, and manage symptoms.

Networking for Patients and Caregivers

The dashboard should actively promote networking among patients and caregivers. It should foster a sense of community, allowing them to connect with others going through similar experiences. This can extend not only to individuals affected by GBM but also to those with other neurological diseases who face similar challenges. Facilitating international connections can provide valuable emotional and social support, as well as promote the exchange of information.

To facilitate these connections, the dashboard should include links to resources to help patients and caregivers find support networks and peer groups, both locally and internationally.

Resource Directory

The dashboard should include a directory of useful resources. This could link to patient organization websites, relevant contact points in different countries, and general support services. This directory should not be limited to brain tumour organizations but should also include resources for rare disease organizations and other relevant networks. The goal is to ensure that users can easily find the help they need, regardless of the disease category. If possible, the dashboard should also provide direct contact information for specific organizations

that are involved in providing support to patients and caregivers.

Q&A Section

To help patients and caregivers navigate the often-overwhelming landscape of information, the dashboard should include a Q&A section. This feature should address common concerns and frequently asked questions about GBM, treatment options, managing symptoms, and more. This will serve as an accessible resource for those looking for quick answers without the need for extensive research.

Collaborating with Patient Organizations

To ensure that the information provided is both accurate and useful, the dashboard should engage with patient organizations. These organizations can offer insights into how best to meet the needs of patients and caregivers and help facilitate networking among them. By working closely with these groups, the dashboard can better serve its users and provide the support they need to cope with the challenges of GBM and other neurological diseases.

Data to Include and Exclude

It is important to carefully consider which types of data are included in the public dashboard. Some kinds of information, especially lifestyle data or psychological data, can be sensitive and potentially stigmatizing for patients. For example, lifestyle factors such as diet, exercise, or substance use may carry implicit judgments that could affect how patients are perceived, especially by outsiders like insurance companies. These data should be presented with appropriate context, clearly explaining why they are being collected and how they contribute to advancing research.

Moreover, lifestyle data could influence decisions made by insurance companies and other entities, potentially leading to discrimination based on these factors. We must be mindful of the risk this could pose to patients and ensure that such information is handled with care. To balance the value of research with patient protection, it is essential to conduct a risk-benefit analysis for each type of data included in the dashboard. This process will help ensure that the benefits of including particular data outweigh the risks to the patients' privacy, dignity, and security.

Promoting the Dashboard Ethically

The promotion of the IPerGlio dashboard must be conducted ethically to ensure that it reaches those who can benefit from it without being exploited or misused. Careful dissemination of information about the dashboard is

essential. It should be promoted to individuals who are directly affected by glioblastoma or those who might be in contact with them, such as patients, caregivers, and health professionals.

It is important to avoid allowing commercial interests to access or exploit the dashboard. The dashboard should be a non-commercial resource that serves the public good, focusing on providing helpful, transparent, and scientifically accurate information. Any partnerships or promotional activities should be scrutinized to ensure that they align with the core mission of the dashboard and do not compromise its integrity.

By focusing on ethical promotion and mindful data inclusion, we can help ensure that the IPerGlio dashboard serves its intended purpose: advancing knowledge while respecting and protecting the rights and dignity of patients and their families.

Conclusion

Conclusion

It is important to promote trust in research and invite patients and their loved ones to contribute, for example by sharing their data. However, maintaining the correct balance between privacy and knowledge facilitation is essential. Patients must have clear control over their data, with the ability to specify how it is used and for what purposes. This approach, an in-between between informed and broad consent, helps prevent data misuse while promoting transparency and trust.

Trust is a cornerstone of successful research. Transparency about data usage, clear communication on research progress, and safeguarding against commercial exploitation are fundamental to maintaining this trust. Information within the dashboard must be regularly reviewed and updated. Patients and their loved ones should be encouraged to participate in research, knowing that their contributions are valued and protected.

Data donation should be recognized as a noble act. Patients should be appropriately thanked for their contribution and researchers should ensure that patients receive updates on how their data is being used and the impact it has on advancing research.

The relationship between researchers and stakeholders should be built on collaboration and mutual respect. Public-facing aspects of research projects should receive adequate financial support, as they are key to patient engagement, education, and community-building. While prioritizing research funding is

essential, investing in outreach and ethical data management is equally critical to ensuring that research remains patient-centred.

By fostering transparency, ethical data management, and patient engagement, dashboard initiatives can serve as a model for future public research initiatives that keep knowledge accessible, prioritize trust, and where contributions from patients make a difference.

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Contact:

Dr. Ruben A. Sakowsky
Juniorprofessur für Medizinische Ethik
mit Schwerpunkt auf Digitalisierung
Fakultät für Gesundheitswissenschaften
Brandenburg, Universität Potsdam
Am Mühlenberg 9, Haus 62 (H-Lab)
14476 Potsdam

Tel.: 0331-977-213842

Mail: ruben.sakowsky@uni-potsdam.de

Web: <https://iperoglio.eu>
<https://iperoglio-germany.eu>

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